

ACRONYM AND ABBREVIATIONS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: Abbreviations are used in written conversation in English as well as in writing. Generally, common abbreviations such as dimensions and headings are always abbreviated in writing. However, days and months are usually written. Online, abbreviations and acronyms are common in texting, chat rooms, and texting. A shortened form of a word or phrase is abbreviated. Acronyms are also a type of abbreviation that can be expressed as a single word.

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Abbreviations and acronyms are shorter versions of existing words and phrases. They're designed to save time and take up less space (whether you're typing or writing by hand), and can even make your writing easier to read. One of the most common types of abbreviations is an abbreviated word. The first few letters of the word or important letters are used for this abbreviation. Common abbreviations include titles used in everyday speech as well as military positions. We have a lot of acronyms, abbreviations and initialisms in English, which we assume most people understand. But even for native speakers, it's not clear what the difference between these three are, and many of them actually come from other languages! According to whatis.com, an acronym is "an abbreviation of several words in such a way that the abbreviation itself forms a pronounceable word. The word may already exist or it can be a new word."¹ There are some famous and international words that few people know were actually formed by putting words or letters together and shortening them.

Any shortened form of a word or phrase is an abbreviation. Acronyms are also a type of abbreviation that can be pronounced as a single word. Abbreviations are selectively used in spoken conversation as well as written English. Generally, common abbreviations such as measurements and titles are always abbreviated in written form. Days and months are commonly written out. Online, abbreviations and acronyms are most common in texting, chat rooms and in SMS. In spoken English, we often use abbreviations in informal conversations. A good rule of thumb is to use abbreviations and acronyms that you know others are familiar with, and avoid them when they are too specific. For example, if you are having a conversation with a business colleague it may be appropriate to use abbreviations particular to your line of work. However, the use of work-related abbreviations would be out of place if speaking with friends. Here is a guide to some of the most common abbreviations. [Using Abbreviations and Acronyms Sparingly](#)²

Avoid using a given acronym unless you use it extensively in a publication. In a short report, do not use an acronym for a phrase you use five or fewer times. In a long report, do not use an acronym for a phrase you use fewer than 10 times. In a webpage, do not use an acronym for a phrase

¹ Bogdanova, V.A. Pismennaya and ustnaya formy nauchnogo style (na material lexicon) [Text] / V.A. Bogdanova. - Saratov, 1999.

² Bolshakov, I. A. O nekotorykh lingvisticheskikh osobennostyakh Delovoy prose. Semiotics and informatics [Text] / I. A. Bolshakov. - M., 1995. -24-33 p.

you use fewer than three times. Some two-letter abbreviations and acronyms are acceptable (e.g., AC and DC, or MW). Avoid other two-letter acronyms that are less universally used. Writing business letters and writing business correspondence today requires high-quality study and a careful approach. When faced with the design and decoding of abbreviations in the business English language for the first time, beginners are sometimes confused and surprised to understand what it all means. The difficulty lies in the correct use of this or that abbreviation, as well as in the peculiarities of the business vocabulary. However, as in any area of language learning, knowledge and a little practice will help overcome any difficulties.

Spelling out Acronyms

In general, each time you use an acronym for the first time in the body of a report or on a given webpage, spell it out and put the acronym in parentheses after the full name. Abbreviations are international organizations (UN, UNESCO), countries and states (PRC, RF, USA), political parties, military associations (UzKDP, NATO), scientific and educational institutions (UzR FA, UzDJTU, FarDU), ministry, office, institution, indicates the names of organizations, enterprises (XTV, DTM, Uzmashholding, Toshshaharyoluchi), machines, equipment and facilities (EHM, ATS, HPP) and others. Q.s ready learning from other languages (UNESCO, FIFA, FIDE, NATO, AES) or a specific language, e.g. can be created on the basis of Uzbek language materials. Most of the Uzbek abbreviations belonging to the next type are Russian word combinations and the forms of abbreviations based on them, for example, BMT < OON, DAN < GAI, OAV (mass media) < SMI (sredstva massovoy informatsii), EHM < EVM, etc.³

In general, the use of abbreviations in English communication registers it is more common than Russian and Uzbek. Not only the names of companies, enterprises, institutions and organizations abbreviated, as well as names of famous people (JFK-John Fitzgerald Kennedy), frequently used concepts (VIP- very important person, Rip-rest in peace (may he rest in heaven); cultural stamps (WASP-Western Anglo-Saxon Protestant), Yuppy-(young urban professional); disease names (SARS –severe acute respiratory syndrome) can also be shortened. It should be remembered that the same abbreviation can express several meanings: ((MP – Member of Parliament, Military police, Metropolitan police, Mounted police), which of them we can find out from the context that it is used in the text.

Characteristics of abbreviations as a special type of nominative signs slow development of many issues related to learning and identification due to, within the framework of studies devoted to nomination problems. A lot of space is devoted to studying the results of abbreviations. In particular, It is of obvious interest to determine the "vocabulary" status of abbreviated names wakes up. This is their category of lexical units includes consideration of their usefulness as verbal cues. So, abbreviations are abbreviations written with letters. For example: UNCTAD - U.N. Conference on Trade and Development. Saving speech and written text is the main task of abbreviation. For voice time according to which the abbreviation is about five times shorter than its corresponding concept and the savings in writing will be more impressive. However, only abbreviations are interlocutors and this saving is justified only in places that are understandable to their translators. Abbreviations are found in texts of various natures and used in various speech styles and speech

³ Galkina, E. N. *Perevod abreviatur i akronimov na russkiy yazyk. Russia and the West: dialogue culture Russia and the West: dialogue culture* [Text] / E. N. Galkina. - M, 2005. -250 p.

activities: newspaper articles, advertising, in letters, artistic works, journalistic and scientific works. Modern business world thanks to the active introduction of new information technologies is distinguished by the most active use of abbreviations in the English language. Information in the materials of the seminar on human rights. Here are examples of abbreviations: 1. FAO - Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) 2. WHO - World Health Organization (World Health Organization) Subject-logical meanings of words in business documents prevail.⁴ That's it together with derivatives of object-logical values in this field of communication except where it is terminological. Diplomatic in this regard a number of features are formed in the speech. One of them is a particularly diplomatic speech the peculiarity of the style is clearly shown. This is a diplomatic speech consists in the existence of a small number of techniques for creating an image. In particular, metonymy, metaphor, as well as the creation of a text or speech image to witness the absence or absence of important and widespread methods possible.

Pay attention to abbreviations and acronyms every professional team related to the development of its own system of abbreviations. Such abbreviations are in dictionaries not reflected, but always out of professional communication has its own definitions. The existence of definitions and explanations of such abbreviations refers to the lack of memorization and activation. All these abbreviations, regardless of their origin, are professional should be considered as limited communication signals. Therefore, recently abbreviations (abbreviations) are words of many languages became one of the most effective ways to replenish wealth. Linguistic perspective. In fact, abbreviations are getting more and more special attention because of their number is growing more and more. Today it is reduced in developed countries the number of lexical units reached tens of thousands. Different abbreviations are widely used in different fields is used. This trend is a natural and scientific-technical phenomenon occurring in the world. It is a unique response of the language to the revolution and the development of international relations. And it is not surprising that abbreviations are a new, rapidly developing science and technology branches: programming, rocket work, cosmonautics, atomic energy, radio electronics, to complete the vocabulary of financial matters and diplomatic correspondence is widely used.

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⁴ Yashnov, P.A. Osobennosti perevoda abbreviation [Text] / P.A. Yashnov. - M., 2005. - p. 289.